

What Reviewers Ask in each section of a Research Paper

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What's IMRaD?

Title

- *Does the title entice the reader?*
- *Is the title concise and informative?*
- *Does the title improve indexing of the article?*
- *Is the title in a declarative format?*
- *Does the title provide a clear indication of the focus of the manuscript?*

Abstract

- *Do the authors describe the overall purpose and hypothesis of the study?*
- *Is the design of the study briefly described?*
- *Are the major findings clearly stated?*
- *Do the authors provide a brief conclusion?*
- *Can the abstract stand on its own? Is it a self-contained summary of the paper?*

Introduction

- *Do the authors provide a rationale for the study?*
- *Is the current status of the field described?*
- *Are the authors missing essential citations?*
- *Do the authors provide a goal or testable hypothesis?*
- *Should any of the text pertaining to context be moved to the discussion?*

Methods

- *Is the study design sound?*
- *Have all necessary ethical approvals been granted and guidelines complied to?*
- *Have all appropriate controls been included?*
- *Does the reporting enable replicability?*
- *Are the statistical analyses appropriate and correct?*

Results

- *Are the findings described in a logical order that mirrors the methods section?*
- *Do the authors support the text with figures, tables, and other graphics/images?*
- *Do the results make sense?*
- *Is there too much/too little detail?*
- *Do the authors interpret the findings and should this be moved to the discussion?*

Discussion

- *Are the major findings accurately described?*
- *Do the authors relate their current findings to previous studies?*
- *Is there any flawed reasoning? Are the arguments logical?*
- *Do the authors describe the limitations of the study and directions for future research?*
- *Are the implications of the study to the field appropriately addressed?*

References

- *Do the authors cite an appropriate number of studies in the introduction and discussion?*
- *Have research studies been cited whenever possible as methodological shortcuts?*
- *Are the authors engaged in excessive self-citation without relevant cause?*
- *Do the authors cite studies in an inclusive, diverse, and unbiased manner?*
- *Have all key references been included?*

Overall,

1. Is the research question valid?
2. Is the study design tailored to answer the research question?
3. Are the results presented clearly and accurately?
4. Are the data compared and contrasted with existing knowledge?
5. Are conclusions supported by the data?

**Would you like to know how to
review other article types?**

**DM me to make peer review
work for you.**

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